

具有波粒二象性的光子，其实既不是波也不是粒子！

A photon with wave-particle duality is neither a wave nor a particle!

很多人在理解光子具有波粒二象性的时候，都会将光子看成是一种粒子或一种波。而将波粒二象性，理解成一种既是波又是粒子的状态。

When many people understand that photons have wave-particle duality, they will see them as a particle or a wave. The wave-particle duality is understood as a state of both a wave and a particle.

其实这是人们对微观状态物质的误解，因为无论是波还是粒子，其实都是宏观世界中物质所呈现出的两种状态。人们之所以会认为光子是波或者粒子的原因，是因为人们以生活中的经验出发，认为微观状态下的物质必然也存在这样两种状态。

In fact, this is a misunderstanding of the microstate of matter, because whether it is waves or particles, there are two states of matter in the macro world. The reason why people think that photons are waves or particles is that people think from the experience in life that the matter in the micro state must also exist

in such two states.

其实微观状态下的电磁波（光），并不是真正意义上的“波”，也不是真正意义上的“粒子”，而是一种电场和磁场状态呈周期性转换的系统。也就是说，电磁波（光）其实是是一种电场与磁场状态呈周期性转换的动态平衡系统。

In fact, the electromagnetic wave (light) in the microstate is not the "wave" in the real sense, nor the "particle" in the real sense, but a system of periodic conversion of electric field and magnetic field state. That is to say, electromagnetic wave (light) is actually a dynamic equilibrium system between electric field and magnetic field.

而这种“电场与磁场状态呈周期性转换的动态平衡系统”，叫作“动态三元平衡系统”。而“三元平衡系统”则是，万物之间遵循“三元平衡定律”而相互作用形成的系统。

This "dynamic equilibrium system of electric field and magnetic field state" is called "dynamic ternary equilibrium system". The "ternary balance system" is a system formed by the interaction of all things following the "ternary balance law".

“三元平衡定律”就是，在一个系统内，两个非平衡状态趋向于

平衡状态的过程，就是三元平衡的过程。

The "law of ternary equilibrium" is a process in which two non-equilibrium states tend to equilibrium, which is the process of ternary equilibrium.

在电磁波的三元平衡中，电场和磁场分别为两个非平衡因素，在电磁波中，电场和磁场的这两种能量的关系，类似于水波中在波峰和波谷位置的两种势能，在水波中波峰处的势能与波谷处的势能，呈周期性的相互转换，而最终形成水波。

In the ternary equilibrium of electromagnetic wave, electric field and magnetic field are two non-equilibrium factors, in the electromagnetic wave, the electric field and magnetic field of the two energy relationship, similar to the water wave in the peak and the trough of the two kinds of potential energy, in the wave peak of the potential energy and trough potential energy, a periodic conversion, and eventually form the water wave.

电磁波在一个波动频率中，电场由强变弱再由弱变强，呈周期性变化，变化的电场周围会形成一个围绕它的磁场。当电场由强变弱时，围绕它的磁场则由弱变强，当电场由弱变强时，围绕它的磁场则由强变弱。因此说电磁波（光），是“电场与磁场呈周期性转换的微观系统”。

Electromagnetic wave In a fluctuating frequency, the electric field changes periodically from strong to weak to weak to strong, forming a magnetic field around it. When the electric field changes from strong to weak, the magnetic field around it changes from weak to strong, and when the magnetic field around it changes from weak to weak. Therefore, the electromagnetic wave (light) is "a microscopic system of periodic conversion of electric field and magnetic field".

任何物质（包括基本粒子、物质、天体等）其实也都是这样的系统，只不过微观状态下的电磁波，相对于其他基本粒子而言，这种状态最为明显。只有这种“电场与磁场呈周期性转换的微观系统”在“三元平衡定律”的进一步作用下，相互间进行复杂的作用，彼此共同形成更加复杂的“三元平衡系统”之后，这种复杂的“三元平衡系统”才会表现出粒子的状态。

Any matter (including elementary particles, matter, celestial bodies, etc.) is also such a system, but the electromagnetic waves in the microscopic state are the most obvious compared to other fundamental particles. Only after this "microscopic system with periodic conversion of electric field and magnetic field" under the further action of "ternary balance law" has a complex interaction and forms a more complex "ternary balance system" together, this

complex "ternary balance system" will show the state of particles.

也就是说，电磁波、电子波、基本粒子、一般物质等，其实都是一种或简单或复杂的“动态三元平衡系统”（电磁场状态呈周期性转换的系统），因此它们其实都具有波粒二象性。

That is to say, electromagnetic waves, electronic waves, elementary particles, general matter, etc., are actually a simple or complex "dynamic ternary equilibrium system" (the electromagnetic field state is periodic conversion system), so they actually have wave-particle duality.

只不过电磁波（光）是这类“动态三元平衡系统”中最基础的一类，电子波、基本粒子、物质等等，则是更加复杂的系统而已。由于电磁波（光）是这类“三元平衡系统”中最基础的一种，所以其“波粒二象性”最明显，而普通物质的“波粒二象性”最弱甚至难以被科学家发现而已。

But electromagnetic waves (light) are the most basic part of this "dynamic ternary equilibrium system", and electron waves, elementary particles, matter, and so on, are even more complex systems. Because electromagnetic wave (light) is one of the most basic of this "ternary balance system", its "wave particle duality" is the most obvious, and the "wave particle duality" of ordinary

matter is the weakest and even difficult to be discovered by scientists.

三元平衡定律:

<https://www.zenodo.org/record/7907583#.ZLvWNnZBxPa>